

Governing synthetic biology: A food policy approach

Summary

- **The UK is recognised as a major global hub for genetic technologies, and food and agriculture are areas in which synthetic biology can be applied.**
- **As the UK has left the EU, there are opportunities to consider the governance of synthetic biology across UK nations through food policies and policymaking processes.**
- **There remains insufficient evidence on attitudes towards the application of synthetic biology to UK food and agriculture, and its governance in the UK.**
- **However, some synthetic biology stakeholders favour a policy approach focussed more on product specifics (i.e., novel traits) rather than the process by which it was produced.**

Recommendations

To support debate and stakeholder input into synthetic biology's governance:

1. Embed a range of stakeholders in decision-making spaces like scientific advisory committees and funding boards.
2. Audit current governance processes with a range of stakeholders regularly, for example, every three years.
3. Use existing research funding mechanisms to incentivise and support future research in the following areas:
 - Social science research on UK attitudes towards synthetic biology's development and trajectory.
 - Synthetic biology research in areas aligning with UK & global food policy priorities.

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The research

As synthetic biology, or engineering biology, advances, its potential to apply to the food and agriculture sectors is becoming more and more evident.

Currently, in the UK, such applications would be governed under a framework of rules and regulations designed to manage novel or genetically modified foods and feed, with a focus on human, animal and environmental health and safety through risk management.

This framework promotes thorough oversight through case-by-case risk assessments.

However, current policy was mainly developed while the UK was a member of the European Union. As this is no longer the case, it is unclear how the UK might govern synthetic biology research, development and commercialisation going forward.

Methods

This brief relies on data from 30 semi-structured interviews with a range of synthetic biology stakeholders.

Interviewees were involved in a broad variety of synthetic biology-relevant roles in the research community, industry, non-governmental organisations, funding, or policymaking.

This data was collected as part of a PhD project designed to answer two linked questions:

1. What are the implications of synthetic biology for UK food policy?
2. What are the implications of relevant UK government policies on the development of food-related synthetic biology in the UK?

Interviews took place between November 2020 and December 2021.

Results

- I. Despite challenges defining the term “synthetic biology”, the field and its applications were perceived as potentially risky for the environment, human health, animal welfare, and potentially ethically questionable in relation to use of animals, unequal distribution of benefits and impact on farmer livelihoods. Synthetic biology was perceived as a growing and expanding field, with the potential for applications to pose problems for current comparator approach-based governance.
- II. Current governance frameworks (including existing GM and Novel Foods regulations) were considered “probably strong enough”, but viewed negatively despite this, as reactive, “onerous” and “draconian”.
- III. Participants advocated for a more product-focussed, rather than process-focussed governance approach. This would involve case-by-case assessment of an application based on its traits and novelty rather than the process by which it was produced. This was viewed as a “logical”, “sensible” approach, more conducive to discussion of risks, benefits and “other legitimate factors” like implications for animal welfare.
- IV. Current food policymaking, developed and entrenched in a fragmented institutional landscape, provides the groundwork for synthetic biology-related food policies to be shaped by a small handful of expert actors and interest groups.
- V. Governance specifically for synthetic biology is dominated by roadmaps and rhetoric, attaching the field’s development to notions of scientific progress and narrowly conceived understandings of economic priorities (funding, investment, commercialisation) as well as risks and benefits.
- VI. Participants did not typically consider food policy considerations to be their

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The results—continued

responsibility, despite widely acknowledging the potential (and current) application of synthetic biology to food and agriculture. This contributed to a sense of “that isn’t what I do” and fragmentation between the field’s actors.

- VII. Perceived opportunities for synthetic biology included heightened public and government awareness and positive perception of genetic technologies in light of COVID-19 vaccinations. It was viewed that there was the political will to review governance of synthetic biology to promote scientific progress. Participants suggested that applications with an environmental focus would align with policy drives like Net Zero and COP agreements.
- VIII. Perceived governance challenges for synthetic biology included difficulties navigating guidance and regulations, untimeliness in approval processes and the possibility that applications might be novel and unsuitable for comparator approach-based governance. Participants also referred to difficulties in trade, due to mismatching approaches to governance across territories, including devolution within the UK and international governance (particularly EU regulations).
- IX. Stakeholders often referred to genetic modification in order to discuss synthetic biology’s definitions, boundaries, futures and relationships with publics and societies. This took two perhaps conflicting forms. First, both proponents and opponents of synthetic biology constructed the field as similar (or the same as) GM either to avoid changes in, or to advocate for, new governance approaches. Second, some suggested that synthetic biology is different to GM (more sophisticated, more developed), to avoid perceived negative public opinions attached to genetic modification.

Detailed recommendations

I recommend that policymakers prioritise the following:

Recommendation one: Embed a range of stakeholders in decision-making spaces like scientific advisory committees and funding boards.

Based on my findings that participants routinely described imaginaries of publics and highlighted the dominance of scientific expertise in policy spaces, current processes might be restrictive of wider debate and opportunities for publics to shape synthetic biology’s trajectory might be missed.

These aspects might also contribute to siloed approaches to governance, not taking a systems view of food policy or considering trade-offs and co-benefits for environment, human health, livelihoods and animal welfare, for example.

Building on the [Regulatory Horizons Council’s \(2022\) recent policy brief](#), in order to take some steps towards balancing the roles of science authority with stakeholder advice, a straightforward approach might be taken wherein a stakeholder advisory panel always reviews and comments on decisions taken by a scientific advisory panel.

An accompanying time limit on decision-making might go some way towards addressing views that current regulatory processes are time consuming, ensuring that advisory committees take authorisation decisions in as timely a way as possible.

Recommendation two: Audit current governance processes with a range of stakeholders regularly, for example, every three years.

Participants viewed synthetic biology as novel, growing and expanding, with potential for

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unforeseen risks and implications for policy. Participants also described a policy process that was reactive to applications emerging.

Both of these points suggest that routine audits of governance processes might be useful. Such audits could be accompanied by horizon-scanning work on synthetic biology's ongoing developments, by civil servants (e.g., researchers in POST) or obtained via rapid reviews funded through existing funding mechanisms.

Reviews should be based in part upon emerging applications and the developments of funded research projects, and their potential implications. They should also consider the effectiveness of procedures for monitoring and evaluation, particularly in cases where formal risk assessment is no longer required under amended GM regulations.

Future research

I recommend the use of existing research funding mechanisms to incentivise and support future research in the following areas:

Area one: UK attitudes towards synthetic biology's development and trajectory.

Participants often made assumptions about the attitudes of publics, based on experiences of GM controversies. These assumptions have long been shown by academic social science scholars to be unrepresentative of the nuanced views of publics.

Making assumptions about public views of synthetic biology based on past attitudes towards GM crops also does not take into account the importance of contextual factors and framings in attitude formation.

Quantitative, qualitative and creative methodologies could be combined to research these attitudes, with an aim of elucidating some ideas about where synthetic biology might go, which futures might be desirable, and which might not.

The contextual importance of social, cultural, political, historical and economic factors should also be explored.

Further, a review of UK news media coverage of synthetic biology and its applications in the UK would also be useful to contextualise any findings on the topic's salience and interest that might be uncovered through public attitudes research.

Area two: Synthetic biology research in areas aligning with UK & global food policy priorities.

Participants often made statements about synthetic biology's potential to provide solutions to food production-related environmental challenges. It was suggested that synthetic biology could play a role in, for example, climate change mitigation and adaptation.

Participants also alluded to synthetic biology's promise for providing 'healthy food' (perhaps, preventing diet-related ill health, such as forms of malnutrition like obesity and hunger), but it is unclear which forms this might take, and participant views on this were vague. Funding could attract research to these areas.

Further, research on the implications, positive and negative, of synthetic biology for the environment, nutrition and farmer livelihoods in food and agriculture would also be of benefit.

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